

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

NATIONAL REPORT DENMARK: MEANINGS OF LONG-TERM CARE NEEDS

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The meanings of long-term care needs in Denmark

Brief summary

There is neither specific and precise definition of the concept of need in Denmark, nor understood within context. It is related to whether individuals are able to perform necessary daily tasks, including personal care. It is the local municipalities that have the responsibility to assess whether the individual has a need and then provide the necessary support whether in the private home or in an institution for long-term care.

1. What are needs?

The concept of needs is it overall difficult to define and understand (Greve 2024), especially when it comes to issues such as long-term care where there can be subjective understanding of what the individual finds is needed from the welfare state.

The information about Denmark provided in the Missoc database shows that there is a very broad definition, with the understanding that: “Any person who is lawfully staying in Denmark is entitled to personal and practical assistance under the Social Service Act if they cannot perform the basic personal and practical activities autonomously, so as to allow them to stay in their home as long as possible and to prevent further loss of physical and mental health.”, see footnote 1.

The legal understanding of how to understand needs is that the aim of assistance is to “improve the capability of the individual recipient to be self-reliant, or to facilitate his/her daily life and enhance the quality of life” § 1(2), and specifically on long-term care that support shall be offered to “persons who are unable to carry out the said activities due to temporary or permanent impairment of physical or mental function or special social problems” (§ 83,2) and “ the municipality shall define individual objectives for assistance” and this shall be “adapted to the recipient’s need on an ongoing basis” § 83,5¹.

¹ Consolidation Act on Social Services, consolidation-act-on-social-services.pdf (sm.dk), accessed the 30th May 2024.

In the historical presentation of the legal background for the municipalities' role², it was in the remarks to the law stated that the services should always be based upon an individual assessment of the need and with the purpose of, if possible, to return to a situation where support is not needed, and further that it should be help to elements that the person temporarily or permanently is not able to do. Thus, a combination of a judgement of the ability to do the ordinary daily task, but also with an aim of trying to help the person to be able to do it again by him/herself. This was later strengthened by an emphasis that rehabilitation should be offered before permanent support were given to an individual (§83A). There is no clear legal definition of need. The focus is that it relates to tasks it is not possible to continue to do. It is albeit also stated that there can be personal care and support, help to necessary practical tasks in the private home, and also food support. Still, a central saying (both in the public debate and in our interviews with stakeholders) has been to be able to "stay in one's own life" for as long as possible. When one is no longer able to live in one's own home there can be access to homes for the elderly.

An indirect understanding of the needs relates to that citizens want that the support they get is coherent and with the same staff (especially related to home-care). Thus, even if needs are not very precise defined there might be indirect and individual understandings of what is needed of support (Social- og Ældreministeriet. 2022).

A consequence of the fact that some needs are perhaps not covered is that there will be unmet-needs. Bradshaw (Bradshaw 1972) was one of the first to use the concept of unmet need. It has been argued that it "occurs in long-term care when a person has disabilities for which help is needed, but is unavailable or insufficient" (Williams, Lyons, and Rowland 1997, 102).

However, this is not simple to define. Five different types of unmet needs have been identified:

Unperceived unmet needs

Subjective, chosen unmet need

Subjective, non-chosen unmet need

Subjective, clinician-validated unmet need

²[19961_L229_som_fremsat.pdf](#) (folketingstidende.dk), accessed the 30th of May 2024

Subjective unmet expectations (Malisauskaite et al. 2021, 3–4).

There might further be a number of reasons for continued unmet needs. This can include the following reasons:

- (a) no longer having such a need;
- (b) having continued needs met;
- (c) having delayed needs met;
- (d) having newly arisen unmet needs; and
- (e) having repeated unmet needs (Vlachantoni et al. 2022).

Thus, a core problem is that “there is not a universally accepted international measure of LTC needs, which makes it difficult to compare eligibility thresholds” (Muir 2017, 18).

It has, with reference to Liddiard been argued that the “definitions of need, whether they are explicit in policies and eligibility rules, or implicit in the decisions made by welfare providers, are rationing devices: they determine who gets what” and with reference to Godfrey and Callaghan that “need is usually defined in terms of demand for existing services” (p. 63). This also highlights the difficulty in measuring unmet needs (Vlachantoni et al. 2011).

A number of definitions and discussions do not necessarily relate to long-term care alone but are broader approaches to the understanding of human needs. With regard to long-term care, needs can be, as argued by some, related to the ability to perform activities of daily living such as movement in bed, transfers, locomotion, dressing, personal hygiene, and feeding (ADL). How many activities a person is not able to do can have an impact on the measurement of unmet needs. Further, there can “normative need (defined by experts or professionals using professional standards), a person’s or group’s felt need (based on their own belief of need) and technical need (when existing provision is made more effective or a new kind of provision is developed)” (García-Gómez et al. 2015, 148).

In the proposal for a new law (decided in December 2024) on care for the elderly there is in the remarks to the suggestion two indirect quotes indicating what can be understood as needs (own translation): "it is the need

for support that the individual's reduced physical or mental functioning or special social problems give rise to, which is the starting point for the assessment" and "an assessed need for help to maintain the daily conduct of life that has arisen in connection with aging" (page 32 and 33)³.

Interviews with the stakeholders in Denmark confirmed that there is no single understanding of the concept. As a stakeholder stated: "Each person's needs are unique. You can't put that down to a formula". The main elements stakeholders mentioned were related to the ability to function in daily life. Some stakeholders divided needs into physical and mental needs and emphasized the importance of both.

Some stakeholders raised the question about who shall decide the needs for the elderly: "What is a bit special of course is the discussion of: Who is it that defines the need? So (...) it has for a long time been the Service law.", another one says that it is the municipalities who defines it: "On the basis of their quality standards, the municipalities have after all defined, what is it that can be done, what is it that we think is a need that it is a municipal's task to help with?". The boundaries of who decides and how this will influence individual access to LTC in the years to come is an open question.

For a more detailed discussion of human needs see (Greve 2024).

2. Needs assessment

In principle, needs assessment have a universal approach. However, there can be differences among municipalities in what that assessment implies for the level of services. It is the local municipalities who make the assessment and are free to choose the way they do this, and they have the obligation to continuously update this review in order to cope with change in the needs of the citizens. The need assessment is based on the whole situation of the household, albeit the starting point is the individual in need of support.

Municipalities typically have persons with professional qualifications doing the needs assessments.

The Board of Appeal⁴ has clarified in an appeal case that support based on the Law on Social Service builds upon the idea that the individual has a responsibility for one's own and family, and that practical support shall

³ [Udkast til forslag til ældrelov.pdf](#) accessed the 6th of September 2024

⁴ [Forsiden — Ankestyrelsen](#) is where citizens can complain about a municipality's decision on the level of service according the judgement of the need of the individual.

be given to tasks that the citizens are not able to do by themselves. If they are not able to do the task, they will first have to try rehabilitation before embarking upon permanent support. Even when having to write quality standards municipalities are not obliged to support if the citizens might do the task themselves. There can however be support with some remedies making the individual able to cope in daily life. Still, if a person is able to use a PC to buy daily necessities online the municipality is not obliged to support with this and not even to pay for the cost of transport of the goods. In recent years also the use of robot vacuum cleaners has been so ordinary within the Danish society that municipalities might ask the elderly to buy these themselves. Thus, access to informal care can have an impact on the level of services delivered, albeit the size is not clear. In principle therefore also that a non-take up is possible, but also not possible to measure.

Assessment might include using what is labelled common language (Fælles Sprog) and can include ADL (Assisted Daily Living) using Barthel Index as an approach (Rostgaard 2015). A guide to health conditions including what to look for is an indirect way to understand how needs are evaluated⁵. It includes elements such as functional abilities (such as ability to do personal care and daily activities), nutrition, mobility, skin and sores, sleep and cognitive abilities. The implication being that a professional qualified by the municipality will have to judge the individual's abilities before making a decision on which type of support can be available for the individual. This might further include an overall evaluation of the household, e.g. if there is a partner who might help to cope with needs.

Thus, needs assessment can be based upon a number of different criteria and different types of needs, and this varies across municipalities. Furthermore, the same needs might be supported differently by municipalities depending on the level decided locally.

3. Stakeholders, spending and structure of long-term care

The rules are set out in laws decided by the parliament, and then the municipalities have the responsibility to implement and deliver the care after assessment of the needs as described above.

⁵ [Guide til helbredstilstande 1.6](#) accessed the 18th June 2024, the paper is from 2022.

This implies that given municipalities have some room for deciding the level of care that there can be variations across municipalities.

Stakeholders includes professionals and their viewpoints, different interest groups and their arguments for what long-term care should be. They can vary from employees, municipalities and citizen's expectations.

A way to understand the development is to look into the amount of people who receive long-term care and the resources spent hereupon. This is done in Table 1 and 2.

In Table 1 is shown data for those receiving different kinds of help at home since 2015.

Table 1: Percentage of people above the age of 67 who has received different types of home care.

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Recipients at 67 years and above of permanent home care (percentage of the population)	12,5	12,2	11,8	11,5	11	11	11	11	11
Recipients at 67 years and above referral to permanent home care (percentage of the population)	12,7	12,4	12	11,8	11,9	12	11,8	11,7	11,6
Recipients at 67 years and above referral to nursing homes/nursing dwellings (percentage of the population)	3,7	3,7	3,6	3,5	3,5
Recipients at 67 years and above of rehabilitation and maintenance rehabilitation (percentage of the population)	2,4	2,3	2,1	2,2	2,1	2	1,9	2	..

Recipients at 67 years and above of preventative home visits (percentage of the population)	21,4	19,8	19,8	18,6	18,3	13,9	13,1	14,7	14,5
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Source: AED21: Service indicators, per cent of the population 67 years and above by region and services (from www.dst.dk). New data May 2025. Accessed the 30th June 2024

The Data in Table 1 is for the whole of Denmark. There are, as mentioned, variations across the municipalities given the different local priorities within the overall rules for the delivery of long-term care. The main change has been that fewer people receive preventative home visits. The data do not inform about the reason why, albeit the age at which the municipalities are obliged to make home visits has increased and most likely also, as a visit is voluntary, more people do not find it important to receive the visit. An indication of that preventative measure might be difficult to implement.

Data do not indicate that there has been austerity in long-term care, see Table 2 and Greve 2020.

Table: 2 Development in spending on old age total, cash and in-kind benefits since 2015

TIME	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total							
EURO per inhabitant	5.744,24	5.555,59	5.703,70	5.867,07	5.993,46	5.955,37	5.824,29
Percentages GDP	12,5	11,8	11,8	12,0	12,1	12,3	11,2
Cash benefit							
EURO per inhabitant	4.957,69	4.769,30	4.913,43	4.948,41	5.061,83	5.032,42	4.877,63
Percentages GDP	10,8	10,1	10,2	10,1	10,2	10,4	9,4

In-kind benefits

EURO inhabitant	per	786,55	786,29	790,28	918,66	931,63	922,95	946,66
Percentages GDP		1,7	1,7	1,6	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,8

Note: EURO is in fixed 2010 prices

Source: Eurostat, spr_exp_fol, accessed the 30th June 2024.

4. Current debates about the need of long-term care

There is an ongoing debate about whether needs are covered sufficiently or not, and there are presently discussions of a new reform of long-term care in Denmark, including how the users' viewpoints can be integrated more into the decision-making process. The debate moreover includes a discussion of long-term care workers' way of organizing their workday. The involves long-term care workers being divided into smaller teams, where they regularly visit the same long-term care users. Organizing teams are up to each municipality. The debate revolves around whether this way of organizing can contribute to users being in a more direct dialogue with long-term care workers on how to provide support to the individual and being able to change the support if the needs change. The stakeholders from the interviews are mostly positive regarding the newer focus on trying to integrate the long-term care user in defining their own needs together with the long-term care staff, but some highlight the risks when defining the needs is more up to the user. "So that self-determination and that dialogue that is written a lot into the new elderly reform. I can see that in the ideological part of it, and I also think that because you shouldn't do anything over people's heads, but it can be special because what do we do if the citizen, every time you come, it is the desire to drink coffee with you. Well, what is the consequence of not taking a shower? Things like that come up."

A legal reform decided late in 2024 have an emphasis on higher involvement of users, and a flexible approach to cope with change in needs for elderly persons.

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